

Prediction model for preloaded injected bolts in double-lapped connections

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ABSTRACT

Preloaded and/or injected bolted connections are commonly used in steel bridges in The Netherlands. The injection of bolts became a good alternative for replacing riveted connections because the injected resin in the bolt-hole clearance increases the slip resistance of the connection. In the design model, according to the standard EN1993-1-8:2011 (1), it is assumed that the resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection is equal to the sum of the two separate resistances from preloading and injection. This research aims to check the above statement and thus investigate the resistance of a “slip-critical” double-lapped joint, including preloading and/or injection.

The conclusion is based on experimental and numerical study, addressing three connection variations. In addition, the Eurocode approach of determining the short-term resistance is considered for two different preloading levels. Each experiment is based on this short-term testing method that complies with the described method of EN1090-2 (2). The numerical analysis is validated by the experimental results and then used to gain insight into the behaviour of the connection.

Based on these results, it can not be concluded that it is safe to assume that the resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection is equal to the sum of the separate resistances obtained from preloading and injection. However, qualification of the conclusion depends on a criterion for measuring relative displacements at specific locations which is addressed in this paper.

Keywords: preloaded and injected bolted connection, slip resistance, double-lapped connection

1 INTRODUCTION

Bolted connections are the most commonly used connection type at construction sites. The goal of the preloaded bolted connection is to assemble components together by mechanical fastening without slip, which is of importance for fatigue resistance. Implementations of these type of connections can be found in cyclically loaded structures such as bridges and supporting structures for wind turbines. In this paper, solely bolted connections with bolts loaded in shear are considered.

The resistance of such connection is created by bearing of the bolt and the adjacent plate and shear resistance of the bolt. This bearing resistance is activated after a certain amount of slip. EN 1993-1-8:2011 (1) distinguishes three types of bolted shear connections. Two of them (B and C) are related to slip-resistant connections, in serviceability and ultimate limit state respectively. One of the advantages of a slip-resistant connection is that it decreases the stress range in the bolt which is subsequently favourable for its fatigue resistance.

In the case of a preloaded bolted connection, an external clamping force is applied which is created by a tensile force within the bolt. This tensile force is the result of a rotation of the nut that clamps the plates together. The reaction is a compressive normal force between the plates of the package. Subsequently, a certain slip-resistance (F_s) is obtained by the preloading and it is mainly dependent on the preload force and the friction at the shear planes of the connection. Another possibility to obtain a slip-resistant bolted connection in shear is to inject the bolt hole by a two-component resin. After injection, the resin hardens and is able to develop resistance against bearing ($F_{b,resin}$). As both approaches have their own advantages, one can question what the resistance is if both load transfer mechanisms are combined. Such implementation can already be found in steel bridges in The Netherlands. According to EN 1993-1-8 (1), it is safe to assume that the resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection is equal to the sum of the separate resistances *Eq. (1)*.

$$F_{s+b,resin} = F_s + F_{b,resin} \quad (1)$$

Where F_s is the slip-resistance of the connection obtained by preloading;
 $F_{b,resin}$ is the bearing resistance of the connection created by the resin;
 $F_{s+b,resin}$ is the resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection.

This formulation of summation, was already introduced by the ECCS (No.79, (3)) in 1994. Where the governing resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection over different plate thicknesses was illustrated. However, an additional study (4) indicated initial doubts about this assumption. From these test data, it came forward that it is not likely that *Eq. (1)* results in conservative outcomes. Based on the research performed (4), the present study was initiated by “the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management – Rijkswaterstaat”.

When looking at the separate components, preloading and injection, EN 1993-1-8 (1) provides models to determine the separate resistances, see *Eq. (2)* and *Eq. (3)*.

$$F_{s,Rd} = \frac{k_s \cdot n \cdot \mu}{\gamma_{M3}} \cdot F_{p,C} \quad (2)$$

Where k_s factor to take into account deviations from the standard hole clearance;
 n number of shear planes;
 μ friction coefficient at the shear plane(s);
 $F_{p,C}$ preload force;
 γ_{M3} partial safety factor;

$$F_{b,Rd,resin} = \frac{k_t \cdot k_s \cdot d \cdot t_{b,resin} \cdot \beta \cdot f_{b,resin}}{\gamma_{M4}} \quad (3)$$

Where d bolt diameter;
 $t_{b,resin}$ effective bearing thickness of the resin;
 β factor to take into account the thickness ratio of middle- and cover plates;
 $f_{b,resin}$ bearing strength of the resin.
 γ_{M4} partial safety factor.

In case of the injected bolted connection, EN1993-1-8 (1) describes that the application of injection does not automatically imply that the connection is slip-resistant since it may belong to connection categories A (non-slip-resistant), B and C. The bearing resistance of the injected bolted connection involves several parameters according to the model of the EN1993-1-8 (1). This model involves parameters that take into account the ratio of the plate thickness of the middle- and cover-plates and between the middle-plate and bolt diameter. For example, if the thickness of the middle-plate is larger than 1.5 times the bolt diameter, the effective thickness at which bearing of the resin considered is limited by 1.5 times the bolt diameter.

2 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

2.1 Test procedure

Annex G of the EN1090-2 (2) defines the experimental procedure to obtain test data for preloaded slip-resistant connections. This procedure defines a specific geometry of the connection and specific locations which need to be considered to measure the relative slip in a connection. But also, criteria, such as an experiment duration between 10 and 15 minutes and the maximum allowed relative slip at which the resistance of a connection is to be determined. Distinction is made between two types of tests, long-term and short-term. In this study, short-term experiments were performed. Therefore, the limit of relative slip was set at a value of 0.15mm at centre bolt group (CBG). Since the considered connection consisted of two side-plates (double-lapped), the relative slip at CBG was determined by averaging the displacement between the middle-plate and each side-plate. This displacement was measured (and recorded) by LVDTs mounted at the edge of the plates, see *Figure 1*.

2.2 Test setup

The goal is to investigate if *Eq. (1)* is a correct approximation of the resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection. Therefore, three different test series (preloading and/or injection) were designed since these types of connections were involved to achieve the goal. In addition, the effect of the level of preload force was investigated. Therefore, two load levels were selected. The first level corresponds to the preload level that is attained when the combined method is applied. This value was determined experimentally and it was specifically aimed for during assembly of the test specimens. Since the level of preload was monitored during the entire experiment, this level could be assured consistently. From these experiments, it turned out that the adopted geometry of involved components resulted in an expected preload force of 140kN after application of this tightening method, instead of a nominally assumed value of 110kN. The maximum difference of the separate preload levels compared to the aimed preload force was 2%. Therefore, the aimed initial preload force of 140kN was ensured sufficiently over all tests. *Table 1* summarises the specifications of all performed tests.

Table 1. Adopted test matrix for this study. Consisting of five different tests with varying configurations

Test	Preloading	Injection	Number of connections	Aimed initial $F_{p,c}$
1	Yes	No	10	140kN
2	No	Yes	10	N/A
3	Yes	Yes	10	140kN
4	Yes	No	6	100kN
5	Yes	Yes	6	100kN

EN1090-2 (2) defines a specific design of the setup to be investigated for slip-resistance connections. To not exceed the capacity of the available testing rig, a different design was adopted. The aim of this new design was to highlight the interaction of preloading and injection. Therefore, the mathematical contribution of bearing strength of the resin is maximised and other mechanisms are suppressed. This contribution is maximised if the thickness of the plates is larger than 1.5 times the bolt diameter (1) and where the thicknesses of the middle- and cover-plates are identical. Both requirements need to be fulfilled. Result was a bolt diameter of 16mm and plates thicknesses of at least 24mm. Standardisation of plate thicknesses led to the implemented thickness of 25mm ($>1.5d$). The edge distances were chosen such that interactions of other failure mechanisms on the measured displacement were expected to be minimised.

To monitor the force in the bolt during preloading and the experiment, strain gauges were installed in the bolt. In order to prevent influence of the shear force in the bolt on the strain gauge measuring the axial force, the bolt was lengthened to place the strain gauges well outside the shear zone. Spacers were installed under the nut for this purpose. *Figure 1* illustrates the experimental setup where the red parts indicate the specimen that is preloaded and/or injected, the single bolt to act as hinge and other components to accelerate the process of changing specimens in the testing rig.

In addition, all slip-resistant shear connections in steel structures, owned by Rijkswaterstaat, need to be provided with a specific coating at the contact surfaces. This coating is applied to improve durability of the connection. The mandatory coating is an Ethyl-Zinc-Silicate coating (5) with a layer thickness of 60 μ m for each surface. The average measured coating thickness was approximately 65 μ m. Besides the type of coating, (5) defines a specific resin to be implemented, namely Huntsman's RenGel SW404 + Ren HY2404.

The installation sequence of preloaded (and injected) bolt connections, requires the first step to be preloading of the bolts. After relaxation, the bolts were retightened. The last step involves, if applicable, injection of the connection. Where the resin hardened for at least eight hours as specified by the manufacturer.

2.3 Experimental results

For the main testing series, an initial preloading force of 140kN was adopted. The average resistance of six preloaded bolted connections was 144.7kN. For the injected bolted connection, the obtained average resistance was 74.7kN. Using equation 3.4 in clause 3.6.2.2.(4) from (1), see Eq. (3), the bearing strength of the resin ($f_{b,resin}$) can be calculated from the test results which constitutes $F_{b,resin}$. This results in a value of $f_{b,resin} = 122$ MPa. From testing data, it turned out that the average resistance of the preloaded and injected bolted connection implementing an initial preload force of 140kN was 187.2kN.

2.4 Analysis of experimental results

From these initial results, it is stated that the obtained resistance from tests on preloaded injection bolted connections is 15% lower than the sum of the separate resistances of only preloaded and only injected connections. Test series 4 and 5 adopted a lower initial preload force of 100kN, instead of 140kN. Serie 4, preload only, resulted in an average resistance of 110kN. For the preloaded and injected bolted connection, the average resistance based on six tests was 158.2kN. Also from these initial results, the average obtained resistance from tests on preloaded injection bolted connections is approximately 15% lower than the sum of the individual resistances of only preloaded and only injected connections, see Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of obtained experimental results for each type of test and implemented preload force.

Type of test	Resistance ($F_{p,C,initial}=140$ kN) [kN]	Resistance ($F_{p,C,initial}=100$ kN) [kN]
Preloading only	144.7	110
Injection only	74.7	74.7
Summation of preload and injection	219.4	184.7
Preloading and injection	187.2 (-15%)	158.2 (-14%)

Figure 1: Overview of designed setup. The red indicated parts are the investigated (preload and/or injected) specimens. LVDTs are located at the pink dots on both sides.

When comparing the results of the two different preloaded bolted connections, it was found that the derived friction coefficient, based on EN1090-2 (2), increased when applying a lower preloading force. This is in line with findings in literature in (6). One could expect that due to the higher preloading force, the quality of the surface roughness decreases such that the friction coefficient decreases. The obtained friction coefficients for tests implementing a preload force of 140kN and 100kN were 0.52 ± 0.029 (mean \pm standard deviation) and 0.55 ± 0.054 respectively. Where it is expected that the standard deviation will decrease after increasing the amount of available datasets. Based on the assumption made (1), one can expect that besides the resistance, also the stiffness can be summed for the separate components. However, from these analyses, it turned out that for two applied initial preload forces, the stiffness could not be simply added. This stiffness is determined within two specific regions:

1. Between the start of the experiment and achieving the slip-resistance;
2. After achieving the maximum slip-resistance.

Within the first region of preloaded bolted connections, the stiffness is mainly governed by the mechanism created by preloading of the bolts. From the test data, it was observed that after achieving the maximum slip-resistance, this resistance was not maintained throughout the entire procedure. The resistance reduces, containing a negative slope in the load-displacement trajectory. This slope was similar for both implemented preload levels (140kN and 100kN). However, for the preloaded and injected bolted connections, a significant difference in stiffness between the two preload levels occurred at the second region (see *Figure 2*). At the point where it is expected that the maximum slip-resistance by preloading is reached, the difference in resistance between the two preload levels was almost 40kN. At the displacement limit of 0.15mm, this difference was reduced to approximately 20kN. Meaning that in the second region, a lower preload level results in a higher stiffness.

After investigating this observation, two possible explanations are stated:

- Due to the increased clamping force, the non-linear displacement along the width of the plates increases. This clamping of the package affects the contribution of the resin by bearing. This behaviour is in line with *Figure 2* and further discussed in *section 4, Figure 6*.
- Interaction of the preload force and shear force. Since the preload force of 140kN is higher than the implemented preload force of 100kN, less resistance is left according to the formulation in (1), see *Eq. (2)*. For the case where actual material properties and a preload force of 140kN are applied, *Eq. (2)* results in $UC=0.9$, while the $UC=0.8$ for an implemented preloaded force of 100kN. Nevertheless, unless closing $UC=1$, a significant drop in preload force was not observed (max.5% of initial available preload force) such that *Eq.(2)* is satisfied.

Figure 2: Load-displacement of four different experiments.

$$\frac{F_t}{1.4 \cdot F_{t,R}} + \frac{F_v}{F_{v,R}} \leq 1.0 \quad (2)$$

Where F_t is the acting normal force at a cross-section;
 $F_{t,R}$ is the resistance in normal direction at a cross-section;
 F_v is the acting shear force at a cross-section;
 $F_{t,R}$ is the resistance in shear direction at a cross-section.

3 NUMERICAL STUDY

A numerical analysis has been performed aiming to compare results in behaviour and give more insight in the activated mechanisms inside the connection. This was done by modelling one connection, consisting of one bolt, in ABAQUS (7).

3.1 Design of numerical model

The geometry of the specimen and the model are identical as shown *Figure 1*. The material properties of the steel plates were chosen as the nominal values, since hardly no influence of the steel plates was expected. However, from performed tests inside the lab the ultimate strength of the bolt is determined and found to be 1232MPa ($f_u = 1232\text{MPa}$, at an assumed plastic strain of 0.2%). The ultimate strength is determined by tensile tests where the load was transferred by two nuts to prevent failure of the threads. The yielding limit was set at a value of 900MPa at a 0% plastic strain. This resulted in a bi-linear material property. The resin was given properties in line with the investigation of Nijgh (8), where an associative flow had been considered for this model. As Young's Modulus and Poisson-factor, 5640MPa and 0.315 were chosen respectively (8). All components are built by solid linear 8-noded-elements. Due to restrictions of the solver, the element type required reduced integration. Therefore, the implemented element is C3D8R, where each solid element had only one single integration point. As implemented solver, the explicit analysis is used. This type of solver was chosen based on two main reasons. The bolt required a preload force (elongation in length) inside the analysis, it is chosen to apply this elongation by a change in temperature. Such option is, in ABAQUS not possible in the ABAQUS/Standard. In addition, it is expected that the behaviour of shear planes is of great importance for the reliability of computed results. According to (9), the explicit solver contains a higher accuracy for friction behaviour compared to implicit solver. Therefore, the explicit solver is used.

3.2 Implemented adaptations

Since the adopted solver is explicit, the system is not unconditionally stable. This instability increases with higher loads or larger element sizes. However, lowering of the loads (by smaller time steps) and reducing the involved mesh sizes, increased the computation time significantly. Balancing between reliable results and optimal computation time resulted in the implementation of mass scaling to accomplish quasi static loading. By increasing the mass of elements, the wave speed reduces since more inertia is involved (10). A reduction of the wave speed results in an increase in maximum implemented time step. Besides scaling of masses, additional adaptations are considered, namely changing the loading mode. The connection was subjected to a displacement load at one end, which generally increases by a constant proportion per time step. However, the *smooth step* option smoothens the loading increments such that at the initial time increment, the specimen was subjected to less load than by the general linear distribution. Since the initial load step involves less loading, the inertia effects reduce, such that stability is more likely.

3.3 Contact interaction

To accomplish physical contact between individual components within the model, contact interactions are implemented. This is done by surface-to-surface contact. In this methodology, all possible interactions are defined by behaviour in normal and tangential direction. In normal direction, perpendicular to the surface area, a *hard contact* is modelled. While in tangential direction, parallel to the surface area, this behaviour involves a penalty.

As penalty, a value of 0.52 is assumed which is based on the calculated friction coefficient of the evaluated test data. In addition, contact properties are defined at the interface between the resin and the bolt, and between the resin and steel plate. From initial numerical results it is observed that the resistance of the injected bolted connection is significantly lower than experiments. Therefore, both contact interaction properties are modified as follows: the interaction with the resin and steel plate is modelled as a rigid connection, while at the contact of the resin with the bolt, the tangential penalty is increased to 0.95 instead of 0.52. The higher friction coefficient results in larger contribution of the resin's shear component to the resistance. This is also as expected since the sides of the bolt, parallel to the loading direction, are expected to transfer force at a certain angle by shear instead of transferring force in normal direction only. Resulting in an additional contribution than only resistance in this longitudinal direction. Therefore, a higher friction coefficient is implemented.

3.4 Analysis of numerical results

From the numerical model, similar resistances as in experiments are observed. For the preloaded bolted connections, the computed numerical resistance (141kN) was 3% lower than the experimental. The numerical prediction of the injected bolted connection gives a resistance of 73.5kN. This is an underestimation of 2%. While for the preloaded and injected bolted connection, the numerical prediction slightly overestimates the resistance, +1% (190kN). An overview of these results are shown in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Overview of numerical and experimental results for an implemented preload force of 140kN

Type of test	Numerical resistance ($F_{p,C,initial}=140\text{kN}$) [kN]	Experimental resistance ($F_{p,C,initial}=140\text{kN}$) [kN]
Preloading only	141.0	144.7
Injection only	73.5	74.4
<i>Summation of preloading and injection</i>	<i>214.5</i>	<i>219.4</i>
Preloading and injection	190 (-11%)	187.2 (-15%)

Despite of the similar resistances between the numerical and experimental analysis, the load-displacement trajectory is not similar. Especially the preloaded bolted connection showed differences between experimental and numerical results. The load-displacement behaviour in experiments contains a decrease after achieving the maximum slip-resistance. While the numerical analysis maintained this maximum resistance, see *Figure 4*. It was expected that damage of the coating resulted in a significant lower (kinetic) friction coefficient and therefore the resistance dropped. In the model, this penalty is constant during the entire procedure. Therefore, no reduction is predicted. Consequently, the summation of separate resistances from experiments show that the summation is close to the actual experimental resistance of the preloaded and injected bolted connections (187kN versus 200kN, see *Figure 4*).

However, these results are close to each other since the curve "Calculated summation preload and injection" calculates the resistance at each separate displacement and thus is not in line with the assumption by the EN1090-2 (2) since this standard states that the resistance of a connection is the maximum applied force within a range below 0.15mm slip. For example, the summation can consist of a contribution of resistance by preloading related to a displacement of 0.025mm while the resin contributes with a certain resistance measured at 0.15mm, based on the predictions.

Therefore, the summed results are close to the obtained resistance for a preloaded and injected bolted connection. Nevertheless, this difference increases if the statement in (2) is assumed. *Figure 3* shows that there is an increased difference between the actual resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection and the summation of separate resistances by experiments. This difference corresponds to the model of the EN1090-2 (2). The main difference is that the preloaded connection does not decrease in resistance anymore and therefore the graph of calculated summed resistance increases, creating this difference of approximately 15% (see *Table 2*).

Figure 4: Load-displacement behaviour for several (calculated) connections, both experiment and numerical. The areas indicate the range of obtained experimental data for each set.

Figure 3. Modified load-displacement behaviour of the separate tests, both experimental and numerical.

3.5 Non-linear contribution of the resin

From experimental data, it is observed that the magnitude of applied preload force has significant effect on the contribution of bearing to the resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection. Numerical results provide more insight in the behaviour of such a connection (see Figure 5). This figure illustrates the acting bearing stresses over the height of the clamping package, 75mm. It was observed that there is a non-uniform contribution of the resin over the height of the clamped plates. The contribution of the resin is substantially lower when a preload force is involved. The stress distributions shown in Figure 5 are obtained at the same measured relative slip of 0.15mm observed at the edge of the plates.

Figure 5: Acting bearing stresses in the resin for several types of connections and preload levels.

According to (2), for short-term experiments, the resistance of a connection is determined up to a maximum measured relative slip of 0.15mm at CBG. In this methodology, it is assumed that the slip is representative for the displacement at the CBG. However, this does not imply that the displacement at the bolt itself is also 0.15mm. Since the displacements at the bolt for different connections is not similar, at identical measured displacement, it can be question if comparison is appropriate. *Figure 6* shows the non-uniform distribution of relative slip along the width of the specimens. As illustrated, the slip at the edge of the plate, where the LVDTs measure, is for all connections 0.15mm. However, at the vicinity of the bolt large variations in relative slip is observed. This non-uniform behaviour depends mainly on the geometry of the connection, number of applied bolts but also the magnitude of the preload force.

Figure 6: Displacement of the specimen over the width of the plates, measured at mid-thickness.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The aim of this research is to investigate if it is safe to assume that the resistance of a preloaded and injected bolted connection is equal to the sum of the separately obtained resistances from preloading and injection. Experimental data showed that when applying a preload force of 140kN, the resistance of a preloaded connection was 144.7kN. For the injected bolted connection, the resistance was 74.7kN. From these results, one would expect that based on the model in EN1993-1-8 (1), the resistance would be 219.4kN. However, it turned out that the actual outcome is 15% lower, namely 187.2kN. This difference in percentage is similar for the case if a preload force of 100kN (-14%) is used. Therefore, based on these results, it can not be concluded that the model in (1), to predict the resistance of the preloaded and injected bolted connection, is safe.

Investigation of both experimental and numerical data showed that the location at which the relative slip is determined, affects the measured resistance significantly. The implementation of the preload force and geometry of the connection play an important role. However, it is not yet known what the actual dependence of the geometry on the experimented resistance is.

Therefore, this study recommends improving knowledge by investigating the effect of geometry and assumed number of bolts on the resistance. It is important to gain more insight in the behaviour of the connection with the goal to see the effect of the preload force. Therefore, it is expected that summation of the resistances is only valid when including a currently unknown weight-factor below one which can be unique for both preloaded and injected resistances. This factor is mainly dependent on the magnitude preload force. Further research might introduce other important parameters to this factor, such as geometry and number of bolts.

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REFERENCES

1. **EN1993-1-8+C2:2011.** *Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-8: Design of joints.* Brussels : CEN, 2011.
2. **EN1090-2:2018.** *Execution of steel structures and aluminium structures - Part 2: Technical requirements for steel structures.* Brussels : CEN, 2018.
3. **ECCS.** *European Recommendations for Bolted Connections with Injection Bolts.* Brussels : s.n., 1994.
4. **Gresnigt, A.M., Bijlaard, FSK and Beg, D.** *Injection bolts in steel structures with short duration high loads.* Timisoara : University of Timisoara, 2012.
5. **Rijkswaterstaat.** *Standaarden RWS - Standaard ROK.* s.l. : Rijkswaterstaat, Dec. 2021.
6. **Natalie Stranghöner et al.** *Execution and reliability of slip resistant connections for steel structures using CS and SS (SIROCO).* Luxembourg : European Union, 2019.
7. **Dassault Systèmes.** *ABAQUS/CAE User's manual.* [Online] 2011. http://130.149.89.49:2080/v6.11/pdf_books/CAE.pdf.
8. **Nijgh, M.P.** *A multi-scale approach towards reusable steel-concrete composite floor systems.* Delft : TU Delft, 2021. ISBN: 978-94-6384-207-5.
9. **Prior, A.M.** *applications of Implicit and Explicit Finite Element Techniques to Metal Forming.* 1994. ISSN: 0924-0136.
10. **Cocchetti, G., Pagani, M. and Perego, U.** *Selective mass scaling and critical time-step estimate for explicit dynamics analyses with solid-shell elements.* Milan : s.n., 2013. ISSN: 0045-7949.